

Constraining Arrays of Numbers in Demography

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Abstract

Demographic work often requires constraining arrays of numbers to controls in one or two dimensions. For example, subnational population projections may be constrained to a national projection. If the results are allowed to take on any nonnegative values, raking solves the problem in one dimension and two-way iterative raking solves it in two dimensions. The problem is more complicated in one dimension if the data can be of any sign, the so-called “plus-minus” problem, as simple raking may produce unacceptable results. This problem is addressed by generalized raking, which preserves the structure of the data at a cost of a nonunique solution. Since demography is concerned with people, which come in whole units, data often have to be rounded to integers. The Cox-Ernst algorithm accomplishes an optimal controlled rounding in two dimensions. In one dimension, the Greatest Mantissa algorithm applies a simplified version of the Cox-Ernst algorithm.

This paper combines into one place all of the above-mentioned problems and techniques. It is written to provide practical guidance to demographers and other practitioners who work with these problems. The demographic variables that can be input to these procedures include population, proportions and rates. The introductory section briefly describes each type of problem and points the reader to the relevant explanatory section. Each section covering either raking or controlled rounding begins with practical advice, followed by a technical discussion and a link to SAS code. Sections combining both raking and controlled rounding link to the relevant raking and controlled rounding sections, along with links to SAS code. All SAS codes are in the form of plug-in macros.

Paper prepared for presentation to the Population Association of America meetings, Los Angeles, CA, 2006. SAS, Base SAS, SAS/IML and SAS/OR are copyrights of The SAS Institute. This report is released to inform interested parties of research and to encourage discussion. The views expressed on methodological and technical issues are those of the author and not necessarily those of the U.S. Census Bureau.

1. Introduction

Demographic work often requires constraining arrays of numbers to controls in one or two dimensions. For example, subnational population projections may be constrained to a national projection. Another example is fine-grained data being constrained to coarser-grained data of higher quality. The final data in every case should, in some way, preserve the structure of the original data. In one dimension, this means that if one initial data element is greater than another, then the transformed elements should preserve this relationship. Optimally, the ratios between elements should be preserved, but this can only be done in the specific case of controlling a vector whose nonzero elements are of the same sign as the control value, with the result left unrounded. Controlled rounding then destroys the ratios, but preserves the order. The effect on the ratios depends on the magnitudes of the initial data elements and unit of rounding. The effect of controlled rounding on these ratios in vectors with large elements relative to the unit of rounding is minimal. On the other hand, initial vectors with elements about the same magnitude as the unit of rounding will find these ratios greatly perturbed. “Generalized raking” (Coleman, 2006a) of a vector of mixed sign or to zero or control of opposite sign to the nonzero data preserves the order of the original elements, while destroying the ratios. The two-dimensional equivalent of raking minimizes a function that measures the distortion from the original matrix.

One-dimensional “raking” multiplies a vector of data by the ratio of the control to the sum of the initial data. Damage to the structure of the original data is avoided only when the control is of the same sign as the nonzero initial data. When the data are of mixed sign or the control is zero or opposite sign of the nonzero data, “generalized raking” takes a weighted average of the ordinarily raked data and the projection of the original data onto the hyperplane defined by the control. The result, except in the cases of a zero control or zero sum, is nonunique. Generalized raking has several advantages over the earlier Akers-Siegel (1965) procedure: a continuous transformation using arithmetic operations is used instead of separate rakes for positive and negative data. It easily handles zeroes in the data. There is never any need to arbitrarily shift and then rake the data, when it is impossible to apply the Akers-Siegel procedure to the original data. When the original data span a wide range of magnitudes, it is possible to simply “stuff” (that is, add) the difference between the control and the sum of the original data to the element of largest absolute value. The choice between stuffing and the generalized rake in these instances is up to the analyst: if the distortion caused by stuffing is minimal, then stuffing may be advised to simplify programming.

The ordinary and generalized rake procedures are geometrically illustrated. The ordinary and generalized rakes define straight lines when viewed as element-wise operations, while the Akers-Siegel procedure defines two rays that intersect at the origin (not shown). The ordinary and generalized rakes are also viewed as projections of a vector onto the hyperplane defined by the control.

Two-dimensional raking, a.k.a. “iterative proportional fitting,” the “RAS algorithm,” and other names, is a much-rediscovered method for constraining a nonnegative matrix to positive row and column controls. The sums of the row and column controls (or “marginals”) must be equal for it to work. It proceeds by alternately raking row data in parallel to row controls and column data to column controls until

convergence. It minimizes a function that measures the distortion of the data. The result is unique. A sufficient condition for feasibility is that the original matrix be positive. When this does not obtain, an algorithm based on linear programming can be used to determine feasibility. Some practical guidance for handling zeroes and “low” (i.e., values too low to be reported) is given to speed convergence. This procedure does not generalize to three or more dimensions: a positive array with positive marginals can still be infeasible.

The Cox-Ernst (Cox and Ernst, 1982) controlled rounding procedure assures that integers are unchanged and nonintegers are rounded to one of their closest integers. A cost to unconventional rounding (that is, rounding in the opposite direction of conventional rounding) is defined and minimized. Because of its complexity, this algorithm is not described in detail. For vectors, the Greatest Mantissa algorithm (Coleman, 2006b) performs controlled rounding by rounding up numbers in order of their mantissas. This simplification of the Cox-Ernst algorithm is simple to describe and program.

Subsection 1.1 provides definitions used in the rest of the paper. Subsection 1.2 provides notation used in the rest of the paper. Subsection 1.3 describes the organization of this paper using hyperlinks. Section 2 describes the algorithms and has links to the SAS codes. Section 3 contains references.

Section 4 contains plug-in SAS macros to implement each procedure. These macros enable the user to use these algorithms immediately without additional programming. A [utility macro](#) to expand sequentially numbered variables is also included.

Section 5 contains figures, already referenced by hyperlinks.

1.1 Some Definitions

Raking:	Multiplicatively constraining data to a control. In two dimensions, this is an iterative process. Also known as “scaling” in the mathematical literature.
Rounding:	Changing a fractional number to an integer.
Conventional Rounding:	The ordinary definition of rounding: changing a fractional number to its closest integer.
Unconventional Rounding:	Rounding a fractional number to an integer other than the closest one. This is, in effect, an “incorrect” rounding.
Stuffing:	Adding the difference between a control and a conventionally rounding vector to the vector’s element of largest magnitude.
Controlled Rounding:	Rounding data to add up to a control.

1.2 Notation

1.2.1 One Dimension

All operations will be performed on the n element vector $\bar{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$. The resulting, transformed vector will be denoted as $\bar{x}' = (x'_1, \dots, x'_n)$. The control value will be c . The

sum of the elements of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ will be denoted as $b = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$. \mathcal{H} is the hyperplane defined by the constraint $c = \sum_{i=1}^n x'_i$. $\lfloor y \rfloor$ is the greatest integer less than or equal to y . $m = y - \lfloor y \rfloor$ is the mantissa or fractional part of y .

1.2.2 Two Dimensions

The original matrix will be denoted by $\mathbf{A} = [a_{ij}]$ with m rows and n columns. The vectors of row and column controls will be denoted by $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = (u_1, \dots, u_m)'$ and $\bar{\mathbf{v}} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$, respectively. The convergence or tolerance criterion will be denoted by *tol*.

1.3 Organization of this Paper

This subsection contains hyperlinks to relevant portions of the paper. It is organized into one- and two-dimensional problems. These two categories contain topics on raking and rounding. Each topic has a brief introduction, with practical advice, a technical discussion, and links to SAS code. Topics that combine raking and rounding are linked to the appropriate raking and rounding topics and to SAS code.

1.3.1 One Dimension

In one dimension, the user has to determine whether the control and nonzero data are of the same sign or not. If the user is unsure, the Generalized Rake is advisable. For choice of controlled rounding algorithm, [click here](#).

1.3.2 Raking when Control and Nonzero Data are of Same Sign (Ordinary Rake)

[Brief description and advice](#)

[Technical discussion](#)

[SAS code](#)

1.3.2.1 Raking Data of Mixed Sign (Generalized Rake)

[Brief description and advice](#)

[Technical discussion](#)

[SAS code](#)

1.3.2.2 Controlled Rounding

Controlled rounding forces a vector $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ to sum up c after rounding. Unless conventional rounding satisfies the constraint, unconventional rounding has to be used. The two

algorithms presented are the [Greatest Mantissa Algorithm](#) and [stuffing](#). The choice of controlled rounding method depends on the structure of the data and user preference. In general, it is best to use the [Greatest Mantissa Algorithm](#). However, when the data vary by several orders of magnitude, [stuffing](#) may be used.

1.3.2.3 Greatest Mantissa Algorithm

[Brief description and advice](#)

[Technical discussion](#)

[SAS code](#)

1.3.2.4 Stuffing

[Brief description and advice](#)

[Technical discussion](#)

1.3.2.5 Raking and Controlled Rounding when Control and Nonzero Data are of Same Sign

SAS code

[Raking and Greatest Mantissa Algorithm](#)

[Raking and Stuffing](#)

1.3.2.6 Raking and Controlled Rounding of Data of Mixed Sign

SAS code

[Raking and Greatest Mantissa Algorithm](#)

[Raking and Stuffing](#)

1.3.3 Two Dimensions

In two dimensions, one loses discretion over choice of methods. Raking must be done using the two-way rake, a.k.a. the RAS algorithm or Iterative proportional Fitting.¹ Controlled rounding must be done using the Cox-Ernst Algorithm.

1.3.3.1 Two-Way Raking

[Brief description and advice](#)

[Technical discussion](#)

¹ That is, if the row and column totals do not themselves need to be estimated, nor are there any constraints on the final values. See Schneider and Zenios (1990) for a discussion of algorithms for problems that do not satisfy these criteria.

[SAS code](#)

1.3.3.2 Controlled Rounding Using the Cox-Ernst Algorithm

[Brief description and advice](#)

[Technical discussion](#)

[SAS code](#)

1.3.3.3 Two-Way Raking and Controlled Rounding

[SAS code](#)

2 Methods Details

2.1 One Dimension

2.1.1 Raking when Control and Nonzero Data are of Same Sign (Ordinary Rake)

Brief description and advice

The ordinary rake simply multiplies every element x_i by c/b :

$$x'_i = x_i \frac{c}{b}. \quad (1)$$

This is simple to program. The essential condition is that the nonzero elements of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ be of the same sign as c .

Technical Discussion

The ordinary rake can be viewed as a projection of the original vector onto the control hyperplane $\{\mathcal{H} \mid \bar{\mathbf{x}} : \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = c\}$. A two-dimensional interpretation is shown in [Figure 1](#). The bold arrow represents $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ and the two arrows combined represent $\bar{\mathbf{x}}'$. Both vectors are collinear, that is, they lie on the same ray. In effect, the ordinary rake stretches or contracts $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ until it contacts \mathcal{H} .

The second interpretation is based on drawing the ray defined by equation (1). We assume that $x_i \geq 0$ for all i . A nonpositive assumption works equally well. [Figure 2](#) shows this ray. The arrow represents the ray from the origin of slope c/b . The linearity of this ray will help the understanding of the generalized rake.

The ordinary rake is monotonic and preserves the structure of the data in both order and ratio. That is,

$$c \begin{matrix} > \\ < \end{matrix} b \Rightarrow x'_i \begin{matrix} > \\ < \end{matrix} x_i \quad \forall x_i \neq 0 \quad (\text{monotonicity}), \quad (2)$$

$$x_i > x_j \Rightarrow x'_i > x'_j \quad (\text{order}), \quad (3)$$

and

$$\frac{x'_i}{x'_j} = \frac{x_i}{x_j} \text{ for all } x_j \neq 0 \text{ (ratio).} \quad (4)$$

Monotonicity means that all nonzero data are shifted in the same direction as the change in their sum. The order property means that the ranking of the data is preserved. When the sign restrictions are relaxed, the ratio property must be lost to preserve the other two.

[SAS code](#)

2.1.2 Raking Data of Mixed Sign (Generalized Rake)

Brief description and advice

The idea behind the general rake is to perturb the ordinary rake so as to preserve the order property. The generalized rake is a weighted average of the ordinary rake and the orthogonal projection of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ onto \mathcal{H} :

$$x'_i = w \frac{c}{b} x_i + (1-w) \left(x_i + \frac{c-b}{n} \right) \text{ for all } i. \quad (5)$$

The value of w has to be determined heuristically. $w = 1$ reproduces the ordinary rake. $w = 0$ is the pure orthogonal projection, the only feasible solution for b or $c = 0$. The heuristic should aim to produce a high (but not the highest, as this leads to a corner solution) value of $w < 1$ to produce an acceptable trade-off between the two pure ($w = 0, 1$) solutions. A practical way to do this is to start with $w = 1$ and decrement w by 0.1 until the order conditions (3) are satisfied. By starting with $w = 1$, the ordinary rake solution is not ignored when it is feasible. Allowing w to equal 0 provides insurance against missing the solution when $c = 0$.² It is possible for w to be negative, when b and c are of opposite sign.

Technical Discussion

[Figure 3](#) shows the vector geometric interpretation of the generalized rake. Vector $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R$ is the transformation of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ using the ordinary rake. Vector $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P$ is the orthogonal projection of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ onto \mathcal{H} . $\bar{\mathbf{x}}'$ lies on \mathcal{H} between these two vectors. Thus, it represents a tradeoff between $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R$ and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P$. w can be understood through the identities

$$w = \frac{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R - \bar{\mathbf{x}}'\|}{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_P\|} \text{ and } 1-w = \frac{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P - \bar{\mathbf{x}}'\|}{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_P\|}. \quad (6)$$

[Figure 4](#) shows the line interpretation of the generalized rake. It is very similar to the ray interpretation of the ordinary rake shown in [Figure 2](#). Instead of being a ray of slope c/b , it is a line of the same slope. Instead of intersecting the x'_i axis at 0, it intersects it at $(1-w) \frac{c-b}{n}$. This shifted intersect reflects the incorporation of the

² If $b = 0$, then computing equation (4) is infeasible and w must be set to 0.

orthogonal projection. Of course, if b or $c = 0$, the slope becomes 0 and the intersection occurs at $\frac{c-b}{n}$.

The generalized rake avoids many of the weaknesses of the Akers-Siegel (1965) procedure, at the cost of having a nonunique solution when both b and $c \neq 0$ (Coleman, 2006a). Further research may be able to refine the algorithm to provide a unique solution.

The generalized rake strengthens the monotonicity condition (2) to

$$c \begin{matrix} > \\ < \end{matrix} b \Rightarrow x'_i \begin{matrix} > \\ < \end{matrix} x_i \quad \forall x_i. \quad (2a)$$

Condition (2a) allows the generalized rake to operate on zero data. Of course, if any zero data represent true zeroes, they should be removed before raking.

[SAS code](#)

2.1.3 Controlled Rounding

2.1.3.1 Greatest Mantissa Algorithm

Brief discussion and advice

The Greatest Mantissa Algorithm (Coleman, 2006b) consists of taking each element of \bar{x} and subtracting the largest integer to obtain the mantissa. That is, $m_i = x_i - \lfloor x_i \rfloor$. Then, assume that the difference between the control and the sum of the largest integers is $k = c - \sum_{i=1}^n \lfloor x_i \rfloor$. The algorithm then rounds up the x_i corresponding to the k largest m_i .

Ties may occur during this procedure: that is, the k th largest mantissa may be shared by multiple x_i . Thus, the user has to implement a tie-breaking procedure.

Technical Discussion

The Greatest Mantissa Algorithm is a one-dimensional simplification of the Cox-Ernst (1982) controlled rounding algorithm. The Cox-Ernst algorithm seeks to 1) preserve integers and 2) minimize unconventional roundings. It does this by assigning a cost to unconventional rounding, which increases in the distance between the original, unrounded data and their unconventionally rounded values. It then minimizes the total cost of rounding. In one dimension, this simplifies to assigning a cost to rounding up mantissas, $c(m_i)$, where $c'(m_i) < 0$, and exists for all m_i , $0 < m_i < 1$. The exact form of c is irrelevant. Unrounded mantissas are costless. Theorem 1 of Coleman (2006b) shows that the cost of rounding is minimized by rounding up the largest mantissas. The generalized rake of this paper can be rounded to integers using this algorithm. Simple modifications of the code can round to other units.

[SAS Code](#)

2.1.3.2 Stuffing

Brief discussion and advice

Stuffing simply takes the difference $c - b$ and adds it to the x_i of largest magnitude. It should only be used when this difference is on the order of a rounding error in the element into which it is added or “stuffed”. Otherwise, the structure of the data may be distorted.

Technical discussion

See [Brief discussion and advice](#).

2.1.4 Raking and Controlled Rounding when Control and Nonzero Data are of Same Sign

[Click here for a discussion of the ordinary rake.](#)

[Click here for a discussion of controlled rounding.](#)

2.1.4.1 Raking and Controlled Rounding Using the Greatest Mantissa Algorithm

[Click here for a discussion of the ordinary rake.](#)

[Click here for a discussion of the Greatest Mantissa Algorithm.](#)

[SAS code](#)

2.1.4.2 Raking and Controlled Rounding Using Stuffing

[Click here for a discussion of the ordinary rake.](#)

[Click here for a discussion of stuffing.](#)

[SAS code](#)

2.1.5 Generalized Raking and Controlled Rounding of Data of Mixed Sign

[Click here for a discussion of the generalized rake.](#)

[Click here for a discussion of controlled rounding.](#)

2.1.5.1 Generalized Raking and Controlled Rounding Using the Greatest Mantissa Algorithm

[Click here for a discussion of the generalized rake.](#)

[Click here for a discussion of the Greatest Mantissa Algorithm.](#)

[SAS code](#)

2.1.5.2 Generalized Raking and Controlled Rounding Using Stuffing

[Click here for a discussion of the generalized rake.](#)

[Click here for a discussion of stuffing.](#)

[SAS code](#)

2.2 Two Dimensions

2.2.1 Two-Way Raking

Brief discussion and advice

The two-way rake, a.k.a. the RAS Algorithm and Iterative proportional Fitting, inter alia, alternately rakes rows and columns to their respective controls (or “marginals”). All elements of the initial matrix \mathbf{A} must be nonnegative. The sum of the row controls must equal the sum of the column controls. The algorithm can be described as follows:³

Step 0. (Initialization) Set $k = 0$ and $\mathbf{A}^0 = \mathbf{A}$.

Step 1. (Row Raking) For $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ define $\rho_i^k = \frac{u_i}{\sum_j a_{ij}^k}$. Define matrix \mathbf{B} by the elements $b_{ij} = \rho_i^k a_{ij}^k$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Step 2. (Column Raking) For $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ define $\sigma_j^k = \frac{v_j}{\sum_i a_{ij}^k}$. Define matrix \mathbf{A}^{k+1} by the elements $a_{ij}^{k+1} = \sigma_j^k b_{ij}$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Step 3. (Convergence Test) Compute $maxdiff = \max_{i,j} |a_{ij}^{k+1} - a_{ij}^k|$. If $maxdiff < tol$ then output \mathbf{A}^{k+1} and stop.

Step 4. Replace k with $k + 1$ and return to Step 1.

The value of tol should be less than the roundoff criterion. For data that are to be rounded to integers, characteristic of demographic data, I like to use 0.5.

This algorithm can be troubled by the presence of zeroes. I recommend replacing zeroes with small values, such as $1e-7$. The end result will “steal” an insignificant amount from the positive entries. This becomes irrelevant if the data are to be rounded afterwards.

Some datasets, such as those in the Bureau of Economic Analysis’s Regional Economic Information System (REIS), come with “low” values suppressed,⁴ but included in summations. Any value that is flagged as low should be replaced with a small, but significant, value less than the threshold for suppressing low values. For example, REIS

³ This is based on Schneider and Zenios (1990, p. 444). It does not matter whether rows or columns are raked first.

⁴ This paper does not address other types of suppression, such as to preserve confidentiality.

values below 5 are flagged and replaced by zeroes. Replacing these values with 1 creates a good starting point. Moreover, this replacement may be necessary for a feasible solution to exist.

For matrices with zeroes, Fagan and Greenberg (1984) describe a procedure to determine the feasibility of the problem. Alternatively, one can compare the output from the two-way rake to the input to see if recoded zero cells have changed significantly. This indicates that the initial problem is infeasible.

Technical details

The algorithm is described in [Brief discussion and advice](#). This problem is a type of matrix balancing problem. See Schneider and Zenios (1990) for a discussion of these problems. Bregman (1967) proved that, for feasible problems, the sequence $\{\mathbf{A}^k\}$ always converges to the unique nonnegative matrix \mathbf{Y} which minimizes $\sum_{i,j} y_{ij} \ln(y_{ij}/a_{ij})$.

Schneider and Zenios (1990) provide additional results and some examples.

[SAS code](#)

2.2.2 Controlled Rounding Using the Cox-Ernst Algorithm

Brief discussion and advice

The basics of the Cox-Ernst Algorithm are discussed in the [discussion of the Greatest Mantissa Algorithm](#). The implementation is from Sands (2003). If the number of significant digits is high, at least two passes are necessary. The first pass should round to the nearest 0.01. The second pass should finish the rounding to integers. In some cases, an additional rounding to intervals smaller than 0.01 in length may be necessary before rounding to the nearest 0.01.

Technical discussion

See Cox and Ernst (1982).

[SAS code](#)

2.2.3 Two-Way Raking and Controlled Rounding

[Click here for a discussion of two-way raking.](#)

[Click here for a discussion of controlled rounding using the Cox-Ernst algorithm.](#)

[SAS code](#)

3 References

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4 SAS Codes

An important note about the SAS codes is that all require SAS 7 or later and that they use SAS/IML. Since the interfaces differ between the two, variables have to be listed individually. Macro [%EXPANDNAME](#) is provided to expand sequentially numbered variables.

Macros [%CTRLROUND](#) and [%RAKEANDROUND2WAYS](#) also require SAS/OR.

Utility SAS Macro %EXPANDNAME

```
%macro EXPANDNAME(STEM,START,END); /* Macro for expanding variable names for macro
calls */
  %do I = &START %to &END;
    &STEM&I
  %end;
%mend EXPANDNAME;
```

Macro %RAKE

```
%macro RAKE(DSIN=,DSOUT=,CTRLDSIN=,VAR=,CTRLVAR=,IDVAR=);

* This macro rakes the data found in variables &VAR in input dataset &DSIN to the ;
* control totals found in variables &CTRLVAR in control dataset &CTRLDSIN. ;
* Optionally, ID variables may specified in &IDVAR, which are read from &DSIN and ;
* placed in the first column(s) of dataset &DSOUT. ;

* Example usage: ;
* No ID variables: ;
* %RAKE(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control dataset>, ;
VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>); ;
* With ID variables: ;
* %RAKE(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control dataset>, ;
VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>, IDVAR=<list of ID ;
variables>); ;

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2; ;

* The output dataset &DSOUT contains the same variable names as the input dataset. ;

* Programmed by Chuck Coleman, April 8, 2004. ;

proc iml;
    use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
    read ALL var {%&VAR} into MATRIX;
    use &CTRLDSIN; * These two statements read in control data;
    read ALL var {%&CTRLVAR} into CTRL;
    RATIO = CTRL / MATRIX[+,,]; * Compute rakes;
    OUTMAT = MATRIX # shape(RATIO,nrow(MATRIX),ncol(MATRIX)); * Apply rakes;
    create XYZPDQ from OUTMAT [colname={%&VAR}]; * Output temporary dataset
XYZPDQ;
    append from OUTMAT;
quit;

* This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
    data &DSOUT;
        merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ;
    run;
%end;
%else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;
    data &DSOUT;
        set XYZPDQ;
    run;
%end;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary dataset XYZPDQ;

proc datasets nolist;
    delete XYZPDQ;
quit;
%mend RAKE;
```

Macro %RAKEANDSTUFF

```
%macro RAKEANDSTUFF(DSIN=,DSOUT=,CTRLDSIN=,VAR=,CTRLVAR=,IDVAR=);

* This macro rakes and stuffs, that is, it constrains data to an integer control by ;
* first raking and then stuffing the difference into the largest cell in each ;
* column, the data found in variables &VAR in input dataset &DSIN to the ;
* control totals found in variables &CTRLVAR in control dataset &CTRLDSIN. ;
* Optionally, ID variables may specified in &IDVAR, which are read from &DSIN and ;
* placed in the first column(s) of dataset &DSOUT. ;

* Example usage: ;
* No ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDSTUFF(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>);
* With ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDSTUFF(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>, IDVAR=<list of ID ;
variables>);

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2;

* IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions. ;

* The output dataset &DSIN contains the same variable names as the input dataset. ;

* Programmed by Chuck Coleman, April 8, 2004. ;

proc iml;
  use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
  read ALL var {%&VAR} into MATRIX;
  use &CTRLDSIN; * These two statements read in control data;
  read ALL var {%&CTRLVAR} into CTRL;
  RATIO = CTRL / MATRIX[+,,]; * Compute rakes;
  OUTMAT = int(MATRIX # shape(RATIO,nrow(MATRIX),ncol(MATRIX)) + 0.5); * Apply
rakes and round;
  free RATIO MATRIX;
  DIFF = CTRL - OUTMAT[+,,]; * Compute differences for stuffing;
  IDX = OUTMAT[<:,,]; * IDX is indexes of column maxima:
elements to be stuffed;
  N = ncol(MAT);
  do I = 1 to N; * Stuffing loop;
    J = IDX[I];
    OUTMAT[J,] = OUTMAT[J,] + DIFF[J];
  end;
  create XYZPDQ from OUTMAT [colname={&VAR}]; * Output temporary dataset
XYZPDQ;
  append from OUTMAT;
quit;

* This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
  data &DSOUT;
    merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ;
```

```
run;
%end;
%else %do;          * No ID variables => straight copy;
  data &DSOUT;
    set XYZPDQ;
  run;
%end;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary dataset XYZPDQ;

proc datasets nolist;
  delete XYZPDQ;
quit;
%mend RAKEANDSTUFF;
```

Macro %GMROUND

```
%macro GMROUND(DSIN=,DSOUT=,VAR=,IDVAR=);

* This macro uses the greatest mantissa method to round the variables &VAR in dataset
&DSIN;
* placing the results into dataset &DSOUT.  Optionally, ID variables can be specified;
* using &IDVAR.  ;

* Example usage: ;
* No ID variables: ;
* %GMROUND(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, VAR=<list of
variables>);
* With ID variables: ;
* %GMROUND(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>,
IDVAR=<list of ID variables>);

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2;

* IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions. ;

* The output dataset &DSOUT contains the same variable names as the input dataset. ;

* Programmed by Chuck Coleman, July 21, 2004. ;

data _NULL_;
  set &DSIN;
  array VARS &VAR;
  X = dim(VARS);
  call symput('NCOLS',X);
  stop;
run;

%let NCOLS1 = %left(&NCOLS);
%let SUMNCOLS = SUM&NCOLS1;
%let VARNCOLS = VAR&NCOLS1;

proc iml;
  use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to
be raked;
  read ALL var {&VAR} into MATRIX;
* use &CTRLDSIN; * These two statements read in control
data;*
  read ALL var {&CTRLVAR} into CTRL;
  RMAT = int(MATRIX); * Integer portions;
  MANTISSAS = MATRIX - RMAT; * Create mantissas;
  SUMS = MANTISSAS[+,]; * Sums of mantissas;
  VARNAMES = "VAR1": "&VARNCOLS";
  create RMAT from RMAT[colname = VARNAMES]; * Output temporary dataset
RMAT;
  append from RMAT;
  create MANTISSAS from MANTISSAS;
  append from MANTISSAS;
  SUMNAMES = "SUM1": "&SUMNCOLS";
  create SUMS from SUMS[colname=SUMNAMES];
  append from SUMS;
```

```

quit;

* Begin implementing Greatest Mantissa Algorithm;

* Use of PROC RANK first suggested by members of Population Estimates Branch;

proc rank data=MANTISSAS out=MANTISSASR;
  var COL1-COL&NCOLS1;
  ranks R1-R&NCOLS1;
run;

* Merge datasets, develop first tie-breaker: size of observation;

data XYZPDQ;
  merge RMAT MANTISSASR;
  array VARS VAR1-VAR&NCOLS1;
  array COLS COL1-COL&NCOLS1;
  array R R1-R&NCOLS1;
  do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
    if abs(VARS[I]) < 1 then R[I] = R[I] + 0.01 * VARS[I]; * Values < 1 get
mapped to .00?;
    else do;
      FIRST_DECIMALS = length(left(put(int(abs(VARS[I])), 12.0)));
      R[I] = R[I] + 0.01 * FIRST_DECIMALS + abs(VARS[I]) * 10 ** -
(FIRST_DECIMALS + 2);
    end;
  end;
  drop I FIRST_DECIMALS;
run;

proc rank data=XYZPDQ out=XYZPDQ1;
  var R1-R&NCOLS1;
  ranks RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
run;

* Implement second tie-breaker: order;

data XYZPDQ;
  set XYZPDQ1;
  array RR RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
  do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
    RR[I] = RR[I] + 1E-7 * _N_;
  end;
  drop I R1-R&NCOLS1;
run;

proc rank descending data=XYZPDQ out=XYZPDQ1;
  var RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
  ranks RRR1-RRR&NCOLS1;
run;

* Finally, round up mantissas, rename variables;

data XYZPDQ;
  set XYZPDQ1(drop = RR1-RR&NCOLS1);
  if _N_ = 1 then set SUMS; * Puts SUM1-SUM&NCOLS1 into every observation;

```

```

array INVARS VAR1-VAR&NCOLS1;
array VARS &VAR;
array RRR RRR1-RRR&NCOLS1;
array SUMS SUM1-SUM&NCOLS1;

do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
    if RRR[I] < SUMS[I] + 1 then VARS[I] = INVARS[I] + 1;
    else VARS[I] = INVARS[I];
end;
*   keep &VAR;
run;

* This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
    data &DSOUT;
        merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ(keep = &VAR);
    run;
%end;
%else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;
    data &DSOUT;
        set XYZPDQ(keep = &VAR);
    run;
%end;

proc print data=&DSOUT;
run;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary datasets;

proc datasets nolist;
    delete XYZPDQ RMAT SUMS MANTISSAS MANTISSASR XYZPDQ1;
quit;

%mend GMROUND;

```

Macro %RAKEANDGMROUND

```
%macro RAKEANDGMROUND(DSIN=,DSOUT=,CTRLDSIN=,VAR=,CTRLVAR=,IDVAR=);

* This macro rakes the data found in variables &VAR in input dataset &DSIN to the ;
* control totals found in variables &CTRLVAR in control dataset &CTRLDSIN. ;
* Optionally, ID variables may specified in &IDVAR, which are read from &DSIN and ;
* placed in the first column(s) of dataset &DSOUT. ;

* The data are further rounded using the greatest mantissa algorithm. ;

* Example usage: ;
* No ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDGRROUND(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>);
* With ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDGRROUND(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>, IDVAR=<list of ID ;
variables>);

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2;

* IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions. ;

* The output dataset &DSOUT contains the same variable names as the input dataset. ;

* Programmed by Chuck Coleman, July 21, 2004. ;

data _NULL_;
  set &DSIN;
  array VARS &VAR;
  X = dim(VARS);
  call symput('NCOLS',X);
  stop;
run;

%let NCOLS1 = %left(&NCOLS);
%let SUMNCOLS = SUM&NCOLS1;
%let VARNCOLS = VAR&NCOLS1;

proc iml;
  use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
  read ALL var {%VAR} into MATRIX;
  use &CTRLDSIN; * These two statements read in control data;
  read ALL var {%CTRLVAR} into CTRL;
  RATIO = CTRL / MATRIX[+,,]; * Compute rakes;
  OUTMAT = MATRIX # shape(RATIO,nrow(MATRIX),ncol(MATRIX)); * Apply rakes;
  RMAT = int(OUTMAT); * Integer portions;
  MANTISSAS = OUTMAT - RMAT; * Create mantissas;
  SUMS = MANTISSAS[+,,]; * Sums of mantissas;
  VARNAMES = "VAR1":"&VARNCOLS";
  create RMAT from RMAT[colname = VARNAMES]; * Output temporary dataset RMAT;
  append from RMAT;
  create MANTISSAS from MANTISSAS;
  append from MANTISSAS;
```

```

SUMNAMES = "SUM1":"&SUMNCOLS";
create SUMS from SUMS[colname=SUMNAMES];
append from SUMS;
quit;

* Begin implementing Greatest Mantissa Algorithm;

* Use of PROC RANK first suggested by members of Population Estimates Branch;

proc rank data=MANTISSAS out=MANTISSASR;
var COL1-COL&NCOLS1;
ranks R1-R&NCOLS1;
run;

* Merge datasets, develop first tie-breaker: size of observation;

data XYZPDQ;
merge RMAT MANTISSASR;
array VARS VAR1-VAR&NCOLS1;
array COLS COL1-COL&NCOLS1;
array R R1-R&NCOLS1;
do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
    if abs(VARS[I]) < 1 then R[I] = R[I] + 0.01 * VARS[I]; * Values < 1 get
mapped to .00?;
    else do;
        FIRST_DECIMALS = length(left(put(int(abs(VARS[I])), 12.0)));
        R[I] = R[I] + 0.01 * FIRST_DECIMALS + abs(VARS[I]) * 10 ** -
(FIRST_DECIMALS + 2);
    end;
end;
drop I FIRST_DECIMALS;
run;

proc rank data=XYZPDQ out=XYZPDQ1;
var R1-R&NCOLS1;
ranks RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
run;

* Implement second tie-breaker: order;

data XYZPDQ;
set XYZPDQ1;
array RR RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
    RR[I] = RR[I] + 1E-7 * _N_;
end;
drop I R1-R&NCOLS1;
run;

proc rank descending data=XYZPDQ out=XYZPDQ1;
var RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
ranks RRR1-RRR&NCOLS1;
run;

* Finally, round up mantissas, rename variables;

```

```

data XYZPDQ;
  set XYZPDQ1(drop = RR1-RR&NCOLS1);
  if _N_ = 1 then set SUMS; * Puts SUM1-SUM&NCOLS1 into every observation;

  array INVARS VAR1-VAR&NCOLS1;
  array VARS &VAR;
  array RRR RRR1-RRR&NCOLS1;
  array SUMS SUM1-SUM&NCOLS1;

  do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
    if RRR[I] < SUMS[I] + 1 then VARS[I] = INVARS[I] + 1;
    else VARS[I] = INVARS[I];
  end;
*   keep &VAR;
run;

* This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
  data &DSOUT;
    merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ(keep = &VAR);
  run;
%end;
%else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;
  data &DSOUT;
    set XYZPDQ(keep = &VAR);
  run;
%end;

proc print data=&DSOUT;
run;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary datasets;

proc datasets nolist;
  delete XYZPDQ RMAT SUMS MANTISSAS MANTISSASR XYZPDQ1;
quit;

%mend RAKEANDGMROUND;

```

Macro %GENRAKE

```
%macro GENRAKE(DSIN=,DSOUT=,CTRLDSIN=,VAR=,CTRLVAR=,IDVAR=);

* This macro rakes the data found in variables &VAR in input dataset &DSIN to the ;
* control totals found in variables &CTRLVAR in control dataset &CTRLDSIN using the ;
* generalized rake. ;
* Optionally, ID variables may specified in &IDVAR, which are read from &DSIN and ;
* placed in the first column(s) of dataset &DSOUT. ;

* Example usage: ;
* No ID variables: ;
* %RAKE(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control dataset>, ;
VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>); ;
* With ID variables: ;
* %RAKE(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control dataset>, ;
VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>, IDVAR=<list of ID ;
variables>); ;

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2; ;

* IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions. ;

* The output dataset &DSIN contains the same variable names as the input dataset. ;

* Programmed by Chuck Coleman, January 28, 2006. ;

proc iml;
    use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
    read ALL var {%&VAR} into MATRIX;
    use &CTRLDSIN; * These two statements read in control data;
    read ALL var {%&CTRLVAR} into CTRL;
    N = ncol(MATRIX); * Number of vectors to rake;
    M = nrow(MATRIX); * Number of observations;
    ALLB = MATRIX[+,]; * Vector to hold all B used in do loop;
    RATIO = CTRL / ALLB; * Compute rakes;
    OUTMAT = J(M, N, 0); * Initialize output matrix;
    do I = 1 to N;
        B = ALLB[I];
        C = CTRL[I];
        if B = C then OUTMAT[,I] = MATRIX[,I]; * Nothing to be done if B = C;
        else if (B = 0 | C = 0) then * B = 0 or C = 0;
            OUTMAT[,I] = MATRIX[,I] + (C - B)/N;
        else do;
            W = 1.1; * Use 1.1 to force W = 1 in first
iteration;
            R = MATRIX[,I] * RATIO[,I]; * Only need to calculate raked vector
once;
            P = MATRIX[,I] + (C - B)/M; * Time-saver: compute orthogonal
projection;
            SIGNUM = sign(C - B);
            COND = 1; * Bug workaround: force execution of do
loop;
            do while (COND);
                W = W - 0.1;
```

```

        Y = W * R + (1 - W) * P;
        if ((Y > MATRIX[,I])[#,] = SIGNUM then do; * Found solution;
            COND = 0;
            OUTMAT[,I] = Y;
        end;
    end;
end;
end;

        create XYZPDQ from OUTMAT [colname={&VAR}]; * Output temporary dataset
XYZPDQ;
        append from OUTMAT;
quit;

* This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
    data &DSOUT;
        merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ;
    run;
%end;
%else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;
    data &DSOUT;
        set XYZPDQ;
    run;
%end;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary dataset XYZPDQ;

proc datasets nolist;
    delete XYZPDQ;
quit;
%mend GENRAKE;

```

Macro %GENRAKEANDSTUFF

```
%macro GENRAKEANDSTUFF(DSIN=,DSOUT=,CTRLDSIN=,VAR=,CTRLVAR=,IDVAR=);

* This macro rakes and stuffs, that is, it constrains data to an integer control by ;
* first raking using the generalized rake ;
* and then stuffing the difference into the largest cell in each ;
* column, the data found in variables &VAR in input dataset &DSIN to the ;
* control totals found in variables &CTRLVAR in control dataset &CTRLDSIN. ;
* Optionally, ID variables may specified in &IDVAR, which are read from &DSIN and ;
* placed in the first column(s) of dataset &DSOUT. ;

* Example usage: ;
* No ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDSTUFF(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>); ;
* With ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDSTUFF(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>, IDVAR=<list of ID ;
variables>); ;

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2; ;

* IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions. ;

* The output dataset &DSIN contains the same variable names as the input dataset. ;

* Programmed by Chuck Coleman, January 28, 2006. ;

proc iml;
  use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
  read ALL var {%&VAR} into MATRIX;
  use &CTRLDSIN; * These two statements read in control data;
  read ALL var {%&CTRLVAR} into CTRL;
  N = ncol(MATRIX); * Number of vectors to rake;
  M = nrow(MATRIX); * Number of observations;
  ALLB = MATRIX[+,]; * Vector to hold all B used in do loop;
  RATIO = CTRL / ALLB; * Compute rakes;
  OUTMAT = J(M, N, 0); * Initialize output matrix;
  do I = 1 to N;
    B = ALLB[I];
    C = CTRL[I];
    if B = C then OUTMAT[,I] = MATRIX[,I]; * Nothing to be done if B = C;
    else if (B = 0 | C = 0) then * B = 0 or C = 0;
      OUTMAT[,I] = MATRIX[,I] + (C - B)/N;
    else do;
      W = 1.1; * Use 1.1 to force W = 1 in first
iteration;
      R = MATRIX[,I] * RATIO[,I]; * Only need to calculate raked vector
once;
      P = MATRIX[,I] + (C - B)/M; * Time-saver: compute orthogonal
projection;
      SIGNUM = sign(C - B);
      COND = 1; * Bug workaround: force execution of do
loop;
```

```

do while (COND);
  W = W - 0.1;
  Y = W * R + (1 - W) * P;
  if ((Y > MATRIX[,I])[#,] = SIGNUM then do; * Found solution;
    COND = 0;
    OUTMAT[,I] = Y;
  end;
end;
end;
end;
free RATIO MATRIX;
DIFF = CTRL - OUTMAT[+,]; * Compute differences for stuffing;
IDX = abs(OUTMAT)[<:,>,]; * IDX is indexes of column maxima:
elements to be stuffed;
N = ncol(MAT);
do I = 1 to N; * Stuffing loop;
  J = IDX[I];
  OUTMAT[J,] = OUTMAT[J,] + DIFF[J];
end;
create XYZPDQ from OUTMAT [colname={&VAR}]; * Output temporary dataset
XYZPDQ;
append from OUTMAT;
quit;

* This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
  data &DSOUT;
    merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ;
  run;
%end;
%else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;
  data &DSOUT;
    set XYZPDQ;
  run;
%end;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary dataset XYZPDQ;

proc datasets nolist;
  delete XYZPDQ;
quit;
%mend GENRAKEANDSTUFF;

```

Macro %GENRAKEANDGMROUND

```
%macro GENRAKEANDGMROUND(DSIN=,DSOUT=,CTRLDSIN=,VAR=,CTRLVAR=,IDVAR=);

* This macro rakes the data found in variables &VAR in input dataset &DSIN to the ;
* control totals found in variables &CTRLVAR in control dataset &CTRLDSIN, using ;
* the generalized rake. ;
* Optionally, ID variables may specified in &IDVAR, which are read from &DSIN and ;
* placed in the first column(s) of dataset &DSOUT. ;

* The data are further rounded using the greatest mantissa algorithm. ;

* Example usage: ;
* No ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDGRROUND(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>);
* With ID variables: ;
* %RAKEANDGRROUND(DSIN=<input dataset>, DSOUT=<output dataset>, CTRLDSIN=<control ;
dataset>, VAR=<list of variables>, CTRLVAR=<list of control variables>, IDVAR=<list of ID ;
variables>);

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2;

* IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions. ;

* The output dataset &DSOUT contains the same variable names as the input dataset. ;

* Programmed by Chuck Coleman, July 21, 2004. ;

data _NULL_;
  set &DSIN;
  array VARS &VAR;
  X = dim(VARS);
  call symput('NCOLS',X);
  stop;
run;

%let NCOLS1 = %left(&NCOLS);
%let SUMNCOLS = SUM&NCOLS1;
%let VARNCOLS = VAR&NCOLS1;

proc iml;
  use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
  read ALL var {%VAR} into MATRIX;
  use &CTRLDSIN; * These two statements read in control data;
  read ALL var {%CTRLVAR} into CTRL;
  N = ncol(MATRIX); * Number of vectors to rake;
  M = nrow(MATRIX); * Number of observations;
  ALLB = MATRIX[+,]; * Vector to hold all B used in do loop;
  RATIO = CTRL / ALLB; * Compute rakes;
  OUTMAT = J(M, N, 0); * Initialize output matrix;
  do I = 1 to N;
    B = ALLB[I];
    C = CTRL[I];
    if B = C then OUTMAT[,I] = MATRIX[,I]; * Nothing to be done if B = C;
```

```

else if (B = 0 | C = 0) then          * B = 0 or C = 0;
    OUTMAT[,I] = MATRIX[,I] + (C - B)/N;
else do;
    W = 1.1;                          * Use 1.1 to force W = 1 in first
iteration;
    R = MATRIX[,I] * RATIO[,I];      * Only need to calculate raked vector
once;
    P = MATRIX[,I] + (C - B)/M;      * Time-saver: compute orthogonal
projection;
    SIGNUM = sign(C - B);
    COND = 1;                          * Bug workaround: force execution of do
loop;
    do while (COND);
        W = W - 0.1;
        Y = W * R + (1 - W) * P;
        if ((Y > MATRIX[,I]))[#,] = SIGNUM then do; * Found solution;
            COND = 0;
            OUTMAT[,I] = Y;
        end;
    end;
end;
free MATRIX RATIO;
RMAT = int(OUTMAT);                  * Integer portions;
MANTISSAS = OUTMAT - RMAT;          * Create mantissas;
SUMS = MANTISSAS[+,];              * Sums of mantissas;
VARNAMES = "VAR1":"&VARNCOLS";
create RMAT from RMAT[colname = VARNAMES]; * Output temporary dataset RMAT;
append from RMAT;
create MANTISSAS from MANTISSAS;
append from MANTISSAS;
SUMNAMES = "SUM1":"&SUMNCOLS";
create SUMS from SUMS[colname=SUMNAMES];
append from SUMS;
quit;

* Begin implementing Greatest Mantissa Algorithm;

* Use of PROC RANK first suggested by members of Population Estimates Branch;

proc rank data=MANTISSAS out=MANTISSASR;
var COL1-COL&NCOLS1;
ranks R1-R&NCOLS1;
run;

* Merge datasets, develop first tie-breaker: size of observation;

data XYZPDQ;
merge RMAT MANTISSASR;
array VARS VAR1-VAR&NCOLS1;
array COLS COL1-COL&NCOLS1;
array R R1-R&NCOLS1;
do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
    if abs(VARS[I]) < 1 then R[I] = R[I] + 0.01 * VARS[I]; * Values < 1 get
mapped to .00?;
    else do;
        FIRST_DECIMALS = length(left(put(int(abs(VARS[I])), 12.0)));

```

```

                R[I] = R[I] + 0.01 * FIRST_DECIMALS + abs(VARS[I]) * 10 ** -
(FIRST_DECIMALS + 2);
            end;
        end;
        drop I FIRST_DECIMALS;
run;

proc rank data=XYZPDQ out=XYZPDQ1;
    var R1-R&NCOLS1;
    ranks RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
run;

* Implement second tie-breaker: order;

data XYZPDQ;
    set XYZPDQ1;
    array RR RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
    do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
        RR[I] = RR[I] + 1E-7 * _N_;
    end;
    drop I R1-R&NCOLS1;
run;

proc rank descending data=XYZPDQ out=XYZPDQ1;
    var RR1-RR&NCOLS1;
    ranks RRR1-RRR&NCOLS1;
run;

* Finally, round up mantissas, rename variables;

data XYZPDQ;
    set XYZPDQ1(drop = RR1-RR&NCOLS1);
    if _N_ = 1 then set SUMS;    * Puts SUM1-SUM&NCOLS1 into every observation;

    array INVARS VAR1-VAR&NCOLS1;
    array VARS &VAR;
    array RRR RRR1-RRR&NCOLS1;
    array SUMS SUM1-SUM&NCOLS1;

    do I = 1 to &NCOLS;
        if RRR[I] < SUMS[I] + 1 then VARS[I] = INVARS[I] + 1;
        else VARS[I] = INVARS[I];
    end;
*   keep &VAR;
run;

* This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do;    * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
    data &DSOUT;
        merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ(keep = &VAR);
    run;
    %end;
%else %do;                    * No ID variables => straight copy;
    data &DSOUT;
        set XYZPDQ(keep = &VAR);

```

```
run;
%end;

proc print data=&DSOUT;
run;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary datasets;

proc datasets nolist;
  delete XYZPDQ RMAT SUMS MANTISSAS MANTISSASR XYZPDQ1;
quit;

%mend GENRAKEANDGMROUND;
```

Macro %RAKE2WAYS

```
%macro
RAKE2WAYS(DSIN=,DSOUT=,ROWCTRLDS=,VAR=,ROWCTRLVAR=,COLCTRLDS=,COLCTRLVAR=,IDVAR=,TOL=);

* Macro RAKE2WAYS rakes the data in dataset &DSIN to the row and column controls
contained;
* in datasets &ROWCTRLDS and &COLCTRLDS, respectively. It does so using the two-way
rake;
* also known as Iterative Proportional Fitting and the RAS algorithm.;

* Required arguments:
;
* DSIN: Input dataset
;
* DSOUT: Output dataset
;
* VAR: Variables to be raked ;
* ROWCTRLDS: Row control dataset
;
* ROWCTRLVAR: Row control variable (just one: all controls are in one column)
;
* COLCTRLDS: Column control dataset ;
* COLCTRLVAR: Column control variables
;

* Optional arguments;
* IDVAR: ID variables to be read from &DSIN and placed in &DSOUT, using Base SAS
syntax ;
* TOL: Tolerance. Default is 0.5.
;

* Output global macro variable &ERRORCODE;
* Value Meaning;
* No error;
* 1 Number of rows do not match;
* 2 Number of columns do not match;
* 3 Controls have inconsistent totals;
* NOTE: All 3 errors may be present: code checks for each error condition
;
* sequentially and stops at first error encountered.
;

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2;

* IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions. ;

* Written by Chuck Coleman, June 29, 2004;

%global ERRORCODE; * Make &ERRORCODE available outside this macro.;
%let ERRORCODE = ; * Clear &ERRORCODE, just in case previous code set it.;

proc iml;
use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
read ALL var {&VAR} into MATRIX;
```

```

        use &ROWCTRLDSIN;                * These two statements read in row
control data;
        read ALL var {&ROWCTRLVAR} into ROWCTRL;
        use &COLCTRLDSIN;                * These two statements read in column
control data;
        read 1 var {&COLCTRLVAR} into COLCTRL;

        %if &TOL ne %then TOL = &TOL;    * Initialize tolerance, default is 0.5;
        %else TOL = 0.5;

        M = nrow(MATRIX);
        N = ncol(MATRIX);
        if nrow(ROWCTRL) ne M then do; * If the numbers of rows do not match, raise
error;
            print 'Numbers of rows do not match';
            call symput('ERRORCODE',1);    * &ERRORCODE can be used by programmer;
            quit;
        end;
        if ncol(COLCTRL) ne N then do; * If the numbers of columns do not match,
raise error;
            print 'Numbers of columns do not match';
            call symput('ERRORCODE',2);
            quit;
        end;
        if sum(ROWCTRL) ne sum(COLCTRL) then do; * If controls do not have equal
sums, raise error;
            print 'Controls do not sum to same total';
            call symput('ERRORCODE',3);
            quit;
        end;

        * Main loop;

        DIFF = 1000; * Initialize DIFF to large value to force execution of do loop;
do until DIFF < TOL;
        OLDMATRIX = MATRIX;
        MATRIX = MATRIX # shape(ROWCTRL / (MATRIX[,+], N, M) `);
        MATRIX = MATRIX # shape(COLCTRL / MATRIX[+,], M, N);
        DIFF = max(abs(MATRIX - OLDMATRIX));
        print DIFF;
    end;
    create XYZPDQ from MATRIX [colname={&VAR}]; * Output temporary dataset
XYZPDQ;
    append from OUTMAT;
    quit;

    %if &ERRORCODE ne %then %do; * Following code is executed if no errors encountered
in PROC IML;

        * This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

        %if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
data &DSOUT;
            merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ;
            run;
        %end;
    %else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;

```

```
        data &DSOUT;
            set XYZPDQ;
        run;
    %end;

    * Clean-up: Delete temporary dataset XYZPDQ;

    proc datasets nolist;
        delete XYZPDQ;
    quit;

    %end;
%mend RAKE2WAYS;
```

%Macro CTRLROUND

```
/* ctrlround */                /* Robert D. Sands, U.S. Bureau of the Census, Washington,
DC, June 13, 2003 */
```

```
/* Controlled rounding program - SAS data set input */
```

```
/* This program performs the controlled rounding of an m x n matrix of real
numbers. The general algorithm is based on a paper by L.H. Cox
and L.R. Ernst (1982) "Controlled Rounding", INFOR (20)4. The
algorithm solves the problem of rounding to adjacent integers of the
real number entries in a tabular array such that the total change
to the table cells is minimized while preserving the tabular structure of the input
array.
```

```
The problem is represented as a capacitated transportation problem as
described in George B. Dantzig (1963) Linear Programming and Extensions, pgs. 377-383.
The solution to the controlled rounding problem using
SAS PROC NETFLOW was first created by Brian Richards and Jim Fagan (1997) at the
U.S. Census Bureau and operated on a fixed size 7 x 7 input matrix.
The current SAS program, which reads an arbitrary m x n matrix
from a text file or a SAS data set and creates the output matrix and SAS data set,
was compiled by Robert Sands (1998) at the Census Bureau.
```

```
The first two data steps, which read in the arbitrarily sized matrix,
were written by Timothy J. Braam (1998) at the Census Bureau.
```

```
In addition, this Macro (Robert Sands, 2003) is designed to have functionality
similar
```

```
to that provided by the conventional SAS® ROUND Function. This is to say that a
round-off unit argument is provided which will produce a table rounded to the nearest
integer,
as well to the nearest ten, hundred, tenth or hundredth.
```

```
*****
*****
```

```
To run this macro, use
%CTRLROUND (DSIN=<input data set name>, DSOUT=<output data set name>,
VAR=<input variable list>);
```

```
Optional arguments are IDVAR=<input ID variable names> and ROUNDOFF=<value>,
the later is required if rounding to a
value other than 1 is desired.
```

```
Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like          ;
VAR1 VA2 X1 X2;
```

```
IDVAR must follow Base SAS conventions.          ;
```

```
*****
*****
```

```
Modified, April 13, June 10, 2004, by Chuck Coleman for E&P
```

```
Note: Datasets PDQXYZ ARCD1 B FTABLE M N NODED SET1 SIGND SOLUTION TTABLE are
reserved for this macro.
```

```
*/
```

```
/* signd */
```

```
/* Find the most significant decimal digit (places to the right of the decimal point)
```

```

    in all the numbers in the tabular array contained in &ds */
%macro signd (ds=,maxwidth=,maxsignd=);
data signd (keep = signd);
    retain signd;
    signd = 0;
    if _N_ eq 1
    then
        do until (last);
            set &ds end=last;
            %do j = 1 %to &cols;
                decimals = substr(put(col&j,&maxwidth.&maxsignd),%eval(&maxwidth - &maxsignd +
1),&maxsignd);
                hold = &maxsignd; found = 0;
                /* Find most significant digit position in col&j */
                do while (hold > 0 and not found);
                    found = substr(decimals,hold,1) ne "0";
                    if not found
                    then
                        hold = hold - 1;
                    end; /* do while (hold > 0) */
                    /* Check if col&j has a more significant digit than previous candidate */
                    if hold > signd
                    then
                        signd = hold;
                    %end;
                end /* do until (last) */;
            else
                do;
                    stop;
                end;
        run;
    %mend signd;

/* prcprint */
%macro prcprint (lib=, ds=, vars=, state=);
proc print data = &lib&ds&state heading = v width = min;
    title "&lib&ds&state";
    format &vars 25.12
    ;
run;
title " ";
%mend prcprint;

%macro ctrlround (dsin=, dsout=, var=, IDVAR=, ROUND OFF=);

    %if &ROUND OFF eq %then %let ROUND OFF = 1; * Default value of &ROUND OFF = 1;

    * First, find out how many variables are in &VAR;

data set1;
    set &dsin;
    array IN &VAR; * Input variables;
    COLS = dim(IN);
    call symput('COLS1',COLS);
run;

%let COLS = %left(&COLS1);

```

```

* Now, rename the variables in &VAR to COL1-COL&COLS;

data SET1;
  set SET1;
  array IN &VAR;
  array COL COL1-COL&COLS;
  do I = 1 to &COLS; * Copy data;
    COL[I] = IN[I];
  end;
  keep COL1-COL&COLS;
run ;

%if &ROUNDOFF ne 1 %then %do;

/* Multiply entries of input data set by inverse of the roundoff unit */
data set1 (drop = total);
  set set1 end=last;
  file PRINT;
  total + col1;
  %do n = 1 %to &cols;
    col&n = col&n * (1/&roundoff);
  %end;
run ;

%end;

/* Find the number in the input data set with the most significant digits to the right of
a decimal point */
%signd (ds=set1,maxwidth=25,maxsignd=12);
/* Process matrix with input data table into data sets needed for
the PROC netflow in order to do controlled rounding of the table */
proc iml;
  /* Read the most significant decimal digit for the numbers in the input data set */
  use signd;
  read all var _num_ into signd;
  B = 10**signd;
  /* Put the base value into a data set */
  create B var {B};
  append;
  /* Read data set with table of real numbers into a matrix */
  use set1;
  read all var _num_ into table;
  tot = sum(table);
  /* Multiply all input matrix enties by base value, B */
  table = table*B;
  /* Determine the number of rows of the input matrix */
  m = nrow(table);
  /* Put the number of rows value into a data set */
  create m var {m};
  append;
  /* Determine the number of columns of the input matrix */
  n = ncol(table);
  /* Put the number of columns value into a data set */
  create n var {n};
  append;

```

```

/* Define the total matrix to hold the input matrix with
the marginal totals */
ttable = j(m+1,n+1,0);
ttable[1:m,1:n] = table;
/* Calculate row marginal totals */
do i = 1 to m ;
    ttable[i,n+1] = sum(table[i,]);
end;
/* Calculate column marginal totals */
do j = 1 to n ;
    ttable[m+1,j] = sum(table[,j]);
end;
ttable[m+1,n+1] = sum(table);
/* Create data set of matrix with marginal totals */
create ttable from ttable;
append from ttable;
/* reset autoname;
print "ttable = " ttable; */

/* Create the 'Folded-in' table from the total table */
ftable = j(m+2,n+2,0);
ftable[1:m,1:n] = mod(table,B);
/* Calculate row node and folded-in values */
do i = 1 to m ;
    ftable[i,n+2] = ceil(sum(ftable[i,1:n])/B)*B;
    ftable[i,n+1] = ftable[i,n+2] - sum(ftable[i,1:n]);
end;
/* Calculate column node and folded-in values */
do j = 1 to n ;
    ftable[m+2,j] = ceil(sum(ftable[1:m,j])/B)*B;
    ftable[m+1,j] = ftable[m+2,j] - sum(ftable[1:m,j]);
end;
ftable[m+1,n+2] = ceil(sum(ftable[m+1,1:n])/B)*B;
ftable[m+1,n+1] = ftable[m+1,n+2] - sum(ftable[m+1,1:n]);
ftable[m+2,n+1] = ceil(sum(ftable[1:m,n+1])/B)*B;
/* Create data set of matrix with folded-in values */
create ftable from ftable;
append from ftable;
/* reset autoname;
print "ftable = " ftable; */

/* Create data sets for input to PROC NETFLOW */

/* Create arrays containing a supply node name and value
representing each interior row (and one for the folded-in row)
and a demand node name and value for each interior column (and one
for the folded-in column) */
_node_ = j(m+1 + n+1,1,' ');
_sd_ = j(m+1 + n+1,1,0);
/* Load supply nodes name and value */
do i = 1 to m+1 ;
    _node_[i,1] = char(i,8);
    _sd_[i,1] = ftable[i,n+2]/B;
end;
/* Add identifying characters to supply nodes of node data */
/* Change all blanks to zeros */
call change (_node_," ", "0",0);

```

```

/* Change 1st 3 characters to 'row' */
call change (_node_,"000","row");
/* Load demand nodes name and value */
do j = 1 to n+1 ;
  _node_[m+1 + j,1] =char(j,8);
  _sd_[m+1 + j,1] = (ftable[m+2,j]/B) * -1;
end;
/* Add identifying characters to demand nodes of node data */
demnode = _node_[m+2:m+1+n+1,1];
call change (demnode," ", "0",0);
call change (demnode,"000","col");
_node_[m+2:m+1+n+1,1] = demnode;
/* Create nodedata data set from arrays for input to PROC NETFLOW */
create noded var {_node_ _sd_};
append;
/* Create arrays containing the arc information: from, to, cost,
  capacity */
_cost_ = j((m+1)*(n+1),1,0);
_from_ = j((m+1)*(n+1),1, ' ');
_to_ = j((m+1)*(n+1),1, ' ');
_capac_ = j((m+1)*(n+1),1,0);
capacity = 1;
p = 2;
do i = 1 to m+1;
  do j = 1 to n+1;
    _cost_[(i-1)*(n+1)+j,1] = (B - ftable[i,j])**p - (ftable[i,j])**p;
    _from_[(i-1)*(n+1)+j,1] = char(i,8);
    _to_[(i-1)*(n+1)+j,1] = char(j,8);
    _capac_[(i-1)*(n+1)+j,1] = capacity;
  end;
end;
/* Add identifying characters to _from_ and to _to_ nodes of arc data */
call change (_from_," ", "0",0);
call change (_from_,"000","row");
call change (_to_," ", "0",0);
call change (_to_,"000","col");
/* Create arcd1 data set from arrays for input to PROC NETFLOW */
create arcd1 var {_from_ _to_ _cost_ _capac_};
append;
quit;

/* Produce solution of controlled rounding using node and arc data sets */
/* The _flow_ variable in the solution dataset output by PROC NETFLOW
  contains either a 0 or a 1 for each cell on the real number matrix
  designating whether it should be rounded the floor integer or rounded
  up to the ceiling integer */
proc netflow nodedata = noded arcd1 arcd1 arcout = solution;
  reset maxit1 = 10000000;
run;

/* Interpret output of PROC NETFLOW and create rounded table */
proc iml;
  /* Get number of rows variable */
  use m;
  read point 1;
  /* Get number of columns variable */
  use n;

```

```

read point 1;
/* Get base variable */
use B;
read point 1;
/* Read input table real numbers into a matrix */
use ttable;
read all var _num_ into ttable;
ttable = ttable/B;
/* Print input table of real numbers with marginal totals */
reset autoname;
/* print ttable; */
/* Create matrix for rounded table */
rtable = j(m+1,n+1,0);
/* Get solution values from PROC NETFLOW output */
use solution;
read all var {_flow_} into flow;
/* Interpret output of PROC NETFLOW and create rounded table */
do j = 1 to n+1;
  do I = 1 to m+1;
    if ((I <= m & j <= n) | (I = m+1 & j = n+1)) then
      /* Create interior cells and total cell from _flow_ variable */
      do;
        if (flow[(j-1)*(m+1)+I,] = 0) then
          rtable[i,j] = floor(ttable[i,j]);
        else /* flow = 1*/
          rtable[i,j] = ceil(ttable[i,j]);
        end;
      else if ((I = m+1 | j = n+1) & ^(I = m+1 & j = n+1)) then
        /* Create row and column marginal cells from _flow_ variable */
        do;
          if (flow[(j-1)*(m+1)+I,] = 0) then
            rtable[i,j] = ceil(ttable[i,j]);
          else /* flow = 1*/
            rtable[i,j] = floor(ttable[i,j]);
          end;
        end;
      end;
    end;
  end;
  /* Print (control) rounded table of integers */
  reset autoname;
  %if %eval(&ROUNDOFF) ne 1 %then %do;
    ttable = ttable*(&roundoff);
    print ttable;
    rtable = rtable*(&roundoff);
    print rtable;
  %end;
  %else %do;
    print TTABLE;
    print RTABLE;
  %end;

  /* Create data set from rounded matrix */
  N1 = nrow(RTABLE)-1;
  RTABLE = RTABLE[1:N1,];
  create PDQXYZ from rtable [colname={&VAR}];
  append from rtable;
quit;

```

```

* This section copies PDQXYZ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

%if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
  data &DSOUT;
    merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) PDQXYZ(keep = &VAR);
  run;
%end;
%else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;
  data &DSOUT;
    set PDQXYZ(keep = &VAR);
  run;
%end;

* Clean-up: Delete temporary datasets;

proc datasets nolist;
  delete PDQXYZ ARCD1 B FTABLE M N NODED SET1 SIGND SOLUTION TTABLE;
quit;
%mend ctrlround;

```

Macro %RAKEANDROUND2WAYS

```
%include 'ctrlround1.sas';    * Remove comment and point to correct file before use;
%macro
RAKEANDROUND2WAYS(DSIN=,DSOUT=,ROWCTRLDS=,VAR=,ROWCTRLVAR=,COLCTRLDS=,COLCTRLVAR=,IDVAR=,
TOL=);

* Macro RAKEANDROUND2WAYS rakes the data in dataset &DSIN to the row and column controls
contained;
* in datasets &ROWCTRLDS and &COLCTRLDS, respectively. It does so using the two-way
rake;
* also known as Iterative Proportionate Fitting and the RAS algorithm. It then calls
macro
* %CTRLROUND to implement Cox-Ernst controlled rounding.;

* Required arguments:
;
* DSIN: Input dataset
;
* DSOUT: Output dataset
;
* VAR: Variables in input dataset to be raked.
;
* ROWCTRLDS: Row control dataset
;
* ROWCTRLVAR: Row control variable (just one: all controls are in one column)
;
* COLCTRLDS: Column control dataset ;
* COLCTRLVAR: Column control variables
;

* Note that variable (except IDVAR) names must be listed individually, like ;
* VAR1 VAR2 X1 X2;

* Optional arguments;
* IDVAR: ID variables to be read from &DSIN and placed in &DSOUT. This list should
follow Base SAS conventions.;
* TOL: Tolerance. Default is 0.5.
;

* Output global macro variable &ERRORCODE;
* Value Meaning;
* 0 No error;
* 1 Negative value in matrix;
* 2 Controls have inconsistent totals;
* 3 Number of rows do not match;
* 4 Number of columns do not match;

* NOTE: All 4 errors may be present: code checks for each error condition
;
* sequentially. Each error is printed to the .lst file. The lowest numbered
;
* error is written to dataset ERRORCODE which the programmer can use.
;
```

```

* Remember to use the arguments followed by the equals sign when invoking macro.
;

* Written by Chuck Coleman, July 21, 2004;

%global ERRORCODE; * Make &ERRORCODE available outside this macro.;
%let ERRORCODE = ; * Clear &ERRORCODE, just in case previous code set it.;

proc iml;
  use &DSIN; * These two statements read in data to be
raked;
  read ALL var {&VAR} into MATRIX;
  use &ROWCTRLDS; * These two statements read in row control
data;
  read ALL var {&ROWCTRLVAR} into ROWCTRL;
  use &COLCTRLDS; * These two statements read in column
control data;
  read point 1 var {&COLCTRLVAR} into COLCTRL;

  TOL = 0.5;
  %if &TOL ne %then TOL = &TOL;; * Initialize tolerance, default is 0.5;

  COMPTOL = 1E-7; * Comparison tolerance;

  M = nrow(MATRIX);
  N = ncol(MATRIX);
  M1 = nrow(ROWCTRL);
  N1 = ncol(COLCTRL);
  SUMROWS = sum(ROWCTRL);
  SUMCOLS = sum(COLCTRL);
  MINMAT = min(MATRIX);
  ERRORCODE = '0';
  if M1 ^= M then do; * If the numbers of rows do not match, raise error;
    print 'Numbers of rows do not match';
    ERRORCODE = '4';
  end;
  if N1 ^= N then do; * If the numbers of columns do not match, raise error;
    print 'Numbers of columns do not match';
    ERRORCODE = '3';
  end;
  if abs(SUMROWS - SUMCOLS) > COMPTOL then do; * If controls do not have equal
sums, raise error;
    print 'Controls do not sum to same total';
    ERRORCODE = '2';
  end;
  if MINMAT < 0 then do; * Negative value encountered in MATRIX;
    print 'Input matrix has a negative value';
    ERRORCODE = '1';
  end;

  if ERRORCODE = '0' then do;

  * Main loop;

  DIFF = 1E9; * Initialize DIFF to large value to force execution of do loop;
  do until (DIFF < TOL);
    OLDMATRIX = MATRIX;

```

```

        MATRIX = MATRIX # t(shape(ROWCTRL / MATRIX[,+], N, M));
        MATRIX = MATRIX # shape(COLCTRL / MATRIX[+,], M, N);
        DIFF = max(abs(MATRIX - OLDMATRIX));
        print DIFF;
    end;

    print (ROWCTRL - MATRIX[,+]);
    print (COLCTRL - MATRIX[+,]);

    create PDQXYZ from MATRIX [colname={&VAR}]; * Output temporary dataset
XYZPDQ;
    append from MATRIX;
    create ERRORCODE from ERRORCODE[colname = 'ERRORCODE'];
    append from ERRORCODE;
    end;
    quit;

    data _NULL_;
    set ERRORCODE;
    call symput('ERRORCODE',ERRORCODE);
    run;

    %if &ERRORCODE eq 0 %then %do; * Following code is executed if no errors
encountered in PROC IML;

        * Control round data in XYZPDQ using the Cox-Enrst algorithm, first pass, using
ROUNDOFF = .01;

        %CTRLROUND(DSIN=PDQXYZ, DSOUT=XYZPDQ, VAR=&VAR, ROUNDOFF = .01);

        * Control round data in XYZPDQ using the Cox-Enrst algorithm;

        %CTRLROUND(DSIN=PDQXYZ, DSOUT=XYZPDQ, VAR=&VAR);

        * This section copies XYZPDQ to &DSOUT, adding ID variables, if desired.;

        %if &IDVAR ne %then %do; * ID variables => using MERGE statement;
            data &DSOUT;
                merge &DSIN(keep = &IDVAR) XYZPDQ;
            run;
        %end;
        %else %do; * No ID variables => straight copy;
            data &DSOUT;
                set XYZPDQ;
            run;
        %end;

        * Clean-up: Delete temporary dataset XYZPDQ;

        proc datasets nolist;
            delete XYZPDQ PDQXYZ;
        quit;
    %end;
%mend RAKEANDROUND2WAYS;

```

5 Figures

Figure 1
Vector Interpretation of Ordinary Rake

Figure 2
Ray Interpretation of Ordinary Rake

Figure 3
Vector Interpretation of Generalized Rake

Figure 4
Line Interpretation of Generalized Rake

